

Self-regulated Learning, Community of Inquiry, and Online Learning Readiness of Filipino Teacher Education Students: Inputs Toward an Enhanced Online Learning Delivery

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Abstract

The need to shift from traditional face-to-face to online learning brought by COVID-19 is both a trend and a challenge to higher education institutions across the world. In this context, a myriad of studies had identified the significance of self-regulated learning (SRL), the community of inquiry (CoI), and online learning readiness (OLR) as essential factors in such a 'shift'. In this study, three hundred thirty-five (335) teacher education students from a state university in Pampanga, Philippines, selected via proportionate stratified random sampling completed an online survey that measured their demographic characteristics, SRL, CoI, and OLR. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) confirmed that CoI significantly differed based on their year levels. Moreover, Pearson's correlation reported a positive moderate relationship between their SRL and CoI at 0.00 and OLR at 0.00 which is lower than 0.01. Conclusively, it is recommended that the results of this study be considered in the institutionalization of an enhanced online learning delivery.

Introduction

The coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has shambled the economies across the globe and affected one and all regardless of nationality, age, and level of education, and has hit even the most vulnerable sectors. Education is no exception. In fact, as of April 20, 2020, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) reported that about 1.5 billion learners across the world were affected due to the implementation of school closures. Meanwhile, due to lockdowns, conventional schooling has been interrupted leaving the students without a choice but to adopt new learning modalities and rely more on their own resources such as smartphones, televisions, and the internet for learning continuity. In higher education, there has been a quick shift from the face-to-face mode of learning to online distance learning challenging universities to reinvent their learning environment to remain relevant and timely (Schleicher, 2020). These circumstances, unprecedented in our lifetimes, particularly the struggles of the higher education sector in this pandemic, made us realize the importance of the urgent need to adapt to an online learning delivery to minimize the threats brought about by the pandemic.

The University of Cambridge was the first institution to quickly adopt online learning for the academic year 2020-2021 (BBC News, 2020). Other universities across the

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Globe have then followed the move. Meanwhile, the Internet evidently obtained a major role in supporting virtual collaborations, online conferences, remote working, and online learning (Favale et al., 2020). In India, online learning is discerned as a remedy to the COVID-19 crisis, although there are various arguments associated with it such as online pedagogy where flexibility, affordability, and accessibility are related (Dhawan, 2020). In Malaysia, where full online classes were implemented both in degree and diploma courses, several challenges are being faced by university students such as internet connectivity, too many different online learning methods, limited broadband data, slow personal laptops and devices, barriers to focus, lack of motivation, limited technical skills, and difficulty in understanding the content (Chung et al., 2020).

In the Philippines, the Department of Health has led the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases intending to flatten the curve and with high hopes of achieving the downward trajectory of CoViD-19 spread through social distancing and lockdown and community quarantine measures (Department of Health [DOH], 2020). With respect to the IATF protocols, online learning has been the saving grace of the Philippine education system for learning continuity amid the COVID-19 pandemic. Drawing back to the birth of online learning in the Philippines, it started to be popular in the country during the early 2000s when Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in government and education grew popular (dela Peña-Bandalaria, 2007). However, in terms of internet connectivity, according to the Speedtest Global Index, the broadband speed of the country was pegged at a low rate of 7.91 Megabits per second (Mbps) in the year 2016. At present, the country has an average broadband speed of 27.07 Mbps which is still way behind its neighboring Southeast Asian countries like Malaysia (90.81 Mbps), Vietnam (59.80 Mbps), and Thailand (183.58 Mbps) (Speedtest Global Index, 2020). Moreover, the Philippines, as a developing country, placed 83rd out of 138 countries in digital readiness in parallel with poverty wherein some families do not have the resources to cope with the demands of online learning. The country, therefore, is not ready for online schooling (Kritz, 2020). Consequently, less privileged families, especially those who do not have access to the Internet, will be left behind or forced to seek other ways of schooling.

Despite all the hindrances brought about by the pandemic, education must be progressive and school administrators and curricularists are expected to develop learning continuity plans. Teachers are expected to be resilient to remain relevant in terms of learning pedagogies while learners are expected to adopt flexible learning options such as online distance education and excel despite the challenges. Also, learners must commit themselves to a worthwhile discourse with their teachers, and colleagues, among others to promote fruitful learning. Community of inquiry (CoI) plays a major role in the critical inquiry of students (Garrison & Akyol, 2011). Online learning researchers have been incorporating CoI because they believe that fruitful learning experiences are achieved through high levels of CoI (Kreijns et al., 2014; Annand, 2011; Cho et al., 2017). It is relevant that such communities may be explored in a timely study.

Due to the increase in the capacity of technology used to deliver learning, online learning practice and online learning readiness of students have gained thrust (Firat & Bozkurt, 2020). Horzum et al. (2015) claimed that a student who is ready for online learning possesses high levels of self-efficacy, academic motivation, demonstration of skills, and information mastery. While online learning readiness is viewed solely as one's ability to adapt to an online environment, number of hours spent in online activities (Firat & Bozkurt, 2020), learner control and self-directed learning (Horzum et al., 2015), and one's meaningful interactions to the online learning environment (Demir, Kaymak & Horzum, 2013) greatly affect online learning readiness of university students.

Self-regulation or self-regulated learning (SRL) has been a topic of interest among scholars because they recognized the significance of this psychological construct in achieving one's ideal and meaningful learning. In fact, despite the academic challenges, students are in need to be resilient and resourceful through self-regulation (Layco, 2020). In online learning, Cho et al. (2017) proved that university students who possess high levels of self-regulation, elicit confidence and motivation because they believe in their capabilities to set learning goals, strategize, monitor, and reflect learning through the synergy between SRL and CoI. Although it is believed that SRL plays a major role in the CoI framework (Cho et al. 2017), Garrison

and Akyol (2011), argued that SRL is the relationship of cognitive presence and teaching presence and not merely a separate piece of the framework. Given these studies, it is of interest to explore the relationship between SRL to CoI of learners.

Community of Inquiry

A community of inquiry (CoI) is a group of people who participate and engage in a collaborative effort of purposeful and meaningful discourse, reflect on personal perception, and confirm consensus (Garrison & Akyol, 2011). Apart from SRL, CoI is a significant factor in the students' meaningful learning. In fact, researchers tackling online learning frequently use the framework of CoI to boost students' learning experiences (Kreijns et al., 2014; Annand, 2011; Cho et al., 2017). Garrison and Akyol (2011) presented the CoI theoretical framework in which three subscales were identified: social presence, cognitive presence, and teaching presence. Due to the lack of direct communication and human touch of online learning (Dhawan, 2020), social presence plays a major role in projecting one's personal identity in cyberspace that he/she is recognized as a 'real' person who progresses through three phases: acquiring a social identity, having purposeful communication, and building relationships (Kreijns et al., 2014). The first subscale of educational CoI is social presence and its role is not just to feel a sense of belongingness, but rather to support critical inquiry to attain learning (Garrison & Akyol, 2011). The second subscale of CoI is cognitive presence. It is the degree to which the students can construct thoughts through continuous discussion and reflection in a community of inquiry (Garrison & Akyol, 2011), whereas meaningful knowledge is being developed through cognitive presence (Cho et al., 2017). Lastly, teaching presence refers to the building, designing, and repurposing of learning materials, as well as facilitating individual and group learning activities (Garrison & Akyol, 2011). In general, it is believed that CoI could expand students' learning experiences because of the three subscales which explore the social aspect, cognitive domain, and materials needed for fruitful and meaningful learning (Annad, 2011).

Online Learning Readiness

The term 'readiness' has been widely used by online learning researchers to determine if students are prepared to embrace the pros and cons of online learning. A growing body of literature has focused on university students' online learning readiness (OLR) (Hung et al., 2010; Naji et al., 2020; Demir Kaymak & Horzum, 2013; Firat & Bozkurt, 2020; Chung, Supramaniam, & Dass, 2020; Horzum et al., 2015). Due to the paradigm shift in the education system brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic, and a growing interest in investigating university students' readiness for online learning, numerous challenges and barriers have surfaced such as poor internet connectivity (Chung et al., 2020), difficulty in adjusting learning styles (Baticulon et al., 2021), lack of direct communication and human touch brought about by communication impediments (Dhawan, 2020), campus traffic (Favale et al., 2020), among others. In view of these studies, Hung et al. (2010), as cited by Chung et al. (2020), identified five (5) dimensions of online learning readiness such as (a) self-directed learning (SDL) that promotes self-control of learning opportunities; (b) learner control that promotes the ability of the student to resist and manage online-related distractions; (c) computer & internet efficacy that encourages student's confidence in using the internet and computer-related resources for successful demonstration of skill; (d) online communication self-efficacy that promotes student's confidence in expressing him/herself in an online platform; and (e) motivation for learning which centers more on willingness and self-driven motivation (intrinsic) of the student in an online class.

Self-regulated Learning

Self-regulation is a popular topic being discussed both in the fields of psychology and education. Self-regulation or self-regulated learning (SRL) is defined as the attainment of learning goals through a student's systematic and self-regulated thoughts and actions (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011a). Students who possess self-regulation tend to perform better than their passive classmates who are just recipients of information (Zumbrunn et al., 2011). When a new task is given, a self-regulated learner sets a learning goal, plans on how to achieve it, monitors their progress toward the goal, and reflects the outcome of

the process (Cho et al., 2017). It is a cyclical process. Moreover, self-regulated learners tend to achieve the highest level in Maslow's hierarchy of needs (Montgomery, 2020), which is self-actualization, and signifies that the learners achieve the full potential of self-fulfillment because of their will (Burman et al., 2015). Consequently, SRL has been vastly associated with various variables such as students' academic achievement (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011a; Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011b; Zumbunn et al., 2011; Broadbent & Poon, 2015; Alghamdia et al., 2019; Alotaibi et al., 2017), mathematical performance (Cleary & Kitsantas, 2017; Layco (2020), English language proficiency (Bai & Wang, 2020), and community of inquiry (Cho et al., 2017).

There are four (4) key qualities a self-regulated learner must possess: (a) intrinsic goal orientation, (b) confidence in learning, (c) control of learning beliefs, and (d) task value (Cho et al., 2017). These four key factors are said to be essential if one is to latch onto SRL's significance. The goal, in its broader sense, is the envisioned result of something that has been planned. Goals in the classroom may be as simple as having a good score in an exam (short-term attainable goal) or having a deeper and broader understanding of the lesson (long-term attainable goal) (Zumbunn et al., 2011). Concerned with the student's character toward content mastery, intrinsic goal orientation implies one's engagement in setting personally significant goals and intentionally monitors, assesses, and modifies the misuse of learning techniques (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011a).

Also, students who self-regulate their learning elicit confidence (Zumbunn et al., 2011). Cho and Jonassen (2009) as cited by Cho et al. (2020) stated that confident students are not just the ones who confidently use deep learning strategies, but also those who strategically participate in online social interactivity which is closely related to students' control of learning beliefs. With that, self-regulated learners believe that they are in control of their own learning resulting in confidence and motivation. In addition to these, task value, which is the discerned value or worth of a particular task (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011b), affects self-regulation. In support of this, a study shows that college mechanical engineering students with high task value are more prepared and planned to accomplish their goals despite the challenges of online learning (Lawanto et al., 2014). Furthermore, effort regulation is also inclined in the SRL process. Broadbent and Poon (2015) stated that effort regulation refers to students' extent to keep on exerting effort despite the academic challenges. These four key qualities along with effort regulation are prerequisites of SRL. Although self-regulation focuses more on systematic personal thoughts, behavior, and actions, a study in online learning suggests that a high level of SRL signifies a stronger sense of community of inquiry (Cho et al., 2017).

With various studies that are concerned with SRL, CoI, and OLR, it could be noted there have been studies that correlated SRL to CoI of university students as well as SRL to OLR, but seemingly, there is no existing study that correlated the three (3) variables together. Moreover, there could be no study that correlated SRL to CoI and OLR from the perspective of Filipino university students. Studies may also be scarce on correlating the three (3) variables in the timely context of the paradigm shift in the education system brought about by the COVID-19 global pandemic.

Considering that the pandemic has brought an unprecedented and out-of-ordinary turn of events particularly in the education system due to the sudden shift from a conventional face-to-face mode of learning to online education. Considering these drastic changes and challenges, and while professors are resilient in preparing classes and adjusting to online pedagogies, university students are found to be struggling in online learning. Despite all the policies and initiatives of the education community, the readiness of Filipino university students for online learning remains questionable (Baticulon et al., 2021). Due to this, online learning readiness of Filipino university students need to be assessed especially when news states that the Philippines is not yet ready for online education (The Manila Times, 2020). Also, Filipino university students' self-regulation must be assessed to interpret how they resiliently adapt to online learning despite the challenges they are facing. Furthermore, Filipino university students' level of community of inquiry must also be assessed to know how they engage themselves in a meaningful discourse leading them to meaningful learning.

This study sought to explore the perspectives of Filipino university students on the identified constructs such as self-

regulation, community of inquiry, and online learning readiness as this may contribute to the growing body of literature about the present status of the education system in the middle of a global pandemic. Also, the significance of an enhanced online learning delivery may be realized in response to the challenges of online education.

Statement of the Problem

Putting into consideration the gaps identified in the literature review, including the timely context in the paradigm shift in the education system, the researchers, therefore, aimed to explore the teacher education students' self-regulated learning, the community of inquiry, and their online learning readiness. Specifically, the following questions were answered:

1. What is the profile of the respondents when described in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. year level; and
 - 1.4. degree program?
2. How may the student respondents self-regulated learning be described along the following subscales:
 - 2.1. intrinsic goal orientation;
 - 2.2. confidence in learning;
 - 2.3. task value;
 - 2.4. control of learning beliefs; and
 - 2.5. effort regulation?
3. How may the student respondents' community of inquiry be described along the following subscales:
 - 3.1. social presence;
 - 3.2. cognitive presence; and
 - 3.3. teaching presence?
4. How may the students-respondents' readiness in online learning be described along the following dimensions:
 - 4.1. computer/internet self-efficacy;
 - 4.2. self-directed learning;
 - 4.3. learner control;
 - 4.4. motivation for learning; and
 - 4.5. online communication self- efficacy?
5. Is there a significant difference in the student-respondents' self-regulated learning, community of inquiry, and online learning readiness when grouped according to their profiles?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the student-respondents' self-regulated learning and their community of inquiry?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the student-respondents' self-regulated learning and their online learning readiness?
8. What inputs toward an enhanced online learning delivery may be proposed to address the results of the study?

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the Filipino teacher education students' projected relationship between SRL, CoI, and OLR. It also shows the connection between SRL to CoI as suggested by Cho et al. (2017) that a high level of self-regulated learning signifies a greater level of community of inquiry. Students who self-regulate their learning have a greater chance of engaging themselves in a purposeful and critical discourse for a meaningful learning experience. It also shows the connection between SRL to OLR, as suggested by Liu and Kaye (2016) that there is a positive relationship between SRL and OLR. Students who self-regulate their learning are confident to demonstrate a skill in cyberspace which signifies a high level of OLR. Furthermore, instructions that are based on self-regulated learning concepts prepare the students to be ready and defeat the challenges of online learning. The framework also shows the exploration of the relationship between SRL and CoI, as well as OLR. Considering the demographic profile of Filipino teacher education students and the interrelationship of SRL to CoI and SRL to OLR, an input for an enhanced online learning delivery may be proposed.

Figure 1.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative, correlational, non-experimental approach was used in the study to describe the relationship of self-regulated learning to the community of inquiry and online learning readiness of teacher education students. It is a cross-sectional survey that captured self-reported data from the respondents in terms of their demographic profile, self-regulated learning (SRL), community of inquiry (CoI), and online learning readiness (OLR). Also, as comparative research, it aimed to test differences in the SRL, CoI, and OLR of the respondents when grouped according to their demographic characteristics such as their age, sex, year level, and degree program. Lastly, as a correlational study, it determined the relationship between SRL and the CoI and OLR of the teacher education students. These designs were found to be fitting and appropriate to provide meaningful results to the problem posed in this study.

Respondents of the Study

Teacher education students from five (5) degree programs of the College of Education of a certain state-funded higher education institution in Pampanga, Philippines were considered as respondents in this cross-sectional study. The said college was recognized by the Commission on Higher Education as a Center of Development in Teacher Education. With this distinction, a rigorous admission process is currently considered in the said institution. The college offers a teacher education

Figure 2.

Number of Samples obtained via Proportionate Stratified Random Sampling

programs, namely: (a) Elementary Education; (b) Physical Education; (c) Secondary Education; (d) Technical-Vocational Teacher Education; and (e) Technology and Livelihood Education. The Secondary Education program has three majors (English, Filipino, and Mathematics); the Technical-Vocational Teacher Education program has two (Food and Service Management & Garments, Fashion, and Technology); and the Technology and Livelihood Education program has two, as well (Home Economics and Industrial Arts). As of the First Semester of the Academic Year 2020-2021, data from the Office of the University Registrar confirms that there were 2,496 students enrolled in various degree programs of the college, with the BEED program yielding the highest student population and the BSEd-Mathematics with the least.

To ensure administrative feasibility in disseminating the online survey questionnaires, a proportionate stratified random sampling was used to identify the target number of students from each stratum, specifically on the basis of the nine programs using the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator.

Instruments

Three self-administered questionnaires which were used by various researchers on the concerned variables were used in this study. Electronic mail was sent to the authors of the questionnaires to obtain a copy and to ask for their permission to use them to gather data pertinent to the objectives. Subscales from Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) (Pintrich et al., 1993), Community of Inquiry (Arbaugh et al., 2008), and the adapted Online Learning Readiness Questionnaire (Chung et al., 2017) were utilized. The entire questionnaire, therefore, was divided into four (4) parts: Part I included the demographic profile of the respondents; Part II included statements to measure the self-regulated learning of the respondents; Part III included statements to measure the community of inquiry; Part 4 included statements to measure the online learning readiness of the respondents.

Part I – Demographic Profile

This part included the respondents' age, sex, year level, and degree program.

Part II – Self-Regulated Learning

The Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) designed and developed by Pintrich et al. (1993) and was modified by Cho et al. (2017) to relate it to the online education context was used in this study to measure self-regulated learning of teacher-education students in online learning. This 20-item questionnaire included the following subscales: (a) intrinsic goal orientation, (b) confidence in learning, (c) task value, (d) control of learning beliefs, and (e) effort regulation. A seven-point Likert scale was used to measure the respondents' level of agreement and disagreement for each statement: 7 – Strongly Agree, 6 – Agree, 5 – More or Less Agree, 4 – Undecided, 3 – More or Less Disagree, 2 – Disagree, 1 – Strongly Disagree. The questionnaire has undergone reliability testing in the study of Cho et al., (2017) using Cronbach's Alpha with a scale reliability index ranging from 0.71 to 0.91 that signified its reliability.

Part III – Community of Inquiry

The Community of Inquiry Questionnaire developed by Arbaugh et al. (2008) and modified by Cho et al. (2017) to measure college students' CoI in online learning was also used in this study. This 23-item questionnaire was divided into three subscales, namely: (a) social presence, (b) cognitive presence, and (c) teaching presence. A seven-point Likert scale was also used to measure the respondents' agreement or disagreement in each statement: 7 – Strongly Agree, 6 – Agree, 5 – More or Less Agree, 4 – Undecided, 3 – More or Less Disagree, 2 – Disagree, 1 – Strongly Disagree. Cho et al., (2017) presented the Cronbach's Alpha results of the questionnaire that ranged from 0.71 to 0.91 and indicated a very reliable characteristic.

Part IV – Online Learning Readiness

The Online Learning Readiness Questionnaire (Hung et al., 2010), designed and modified by Chung, Supramaniam, & Dass (2020) was used to measure the readiness of university students as they venture into online learning. This 21-item questionnaire was divided into five (5) subscales: (a) computer/internet self-efficacy, (b) self-directed learning, (c) learner control), (d) motivation for learning, and (e) online communication self-efficacy. Hung et al. (2010) reported scale reliabilities ranging from 0.727 to 0.871 while Chung, Supramaniam, & Dass (2020) reported alpha values ranging from 0.841 to 0.911. A six-point Likert scale was used to measure the respondents' level of agreement and disagreement for each statement: 6 - Strongly Agree, 5 - Agree, 4 - Slightly agree, 3 - Slightly Disagree, 2 - Disagree, 1 - Strongly Disagree.

A very high-reliability index was obtained from the initial administration of the entire questionnaire to non-participating teacher education students from other campuses of the university as evidenced by an alpha value of 0.97 via Cronbach's alpha.

Procedure

The procedure outlines the step-by-step process followed in conducting the research. This includes how the study was carried out, from the initial stages of participant recruitment to the final data analysis. The procedure section provides a detailed description of how each phase of the research was executed, including the timing, setting, and any interventions or treatments applied. It ensures that the study can be replicated by others, providing transparency and consistency in how the research was conducted.

A letter of permission was sent to the Dean of the College of Education prior to the administration of the online survey to the student respondents. Meanwhile, the documented form of the questionnaire was placed in Google form and was sent to the student-respondents via Facebook messenger as it is the common way of data gathering, due to limited face-to-face interactions.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Obtained data from the online survey were tallied in Microsoft 365 Excel to facilitate the encoding process. Then, all statistical treatments were run using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 25. In order to describe the profile of the respondents, frequency count, and percentage distribution were used. Meanwhile, descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were utilized for the assessment of respondents' self-regulated learning, community of inquiry, and online learning readiness. Moreover, inferential statistics such as the t-test (when variables are grouped according to sex) and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) (when variables are grouped according to age, year level, and degree program) were used to test differences and Pearson r correlation to test relationships. Before the parametric analysis, the tests of normality such as Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk were computed to verify if the data were appropriate for parametric data analysis.

In order to interpret the mean scores of each item in the three questionnaires, the following set of values were used for the Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) Community of Inquiry Questionnaire (seven-point scale), and Online Learning Readiness Questionnaire (six-point scale).

Scale	Rating	Description	Scale	Rating	Description
7	6.17 – 7.00	Strongly Agree	6	5.16 – 6.00	Strongly Agree
6	5.31 – 6.16	Agree	5	4.33 – 5.15	Agree
5	4.45 – 5.30	More or Less Agree	4	3.50 – 4.32	Slightly Agree
4	3.59 – 4.44	Undecided	3	2.67 - 3.49	Slightly Disagree
3	2.73 - 3.58	More or Less Disagree	2	1.84 - 2.66	Disagree
2	1.87 - 2.72	Disagree	1	1.00 - 1.83	Strongly Disagree
1	1.00 - 1.86	Strongly Disagree			

Ethical Considerations

Prior to, during, and after the accomplishment of the study, all ethical considerations were adhered to accordingly to facilitate the scientific, yet ethical conduct of the study. Prior to the dissemination of the online survey, permission from the

Dean of the College of Education was sought. This is to ensure that proper courtesy was observed. The names of the student-respondents were not included in the survey to maintain their anonymity. Respondents were informed of the purpose of the study as it was included in the instruction at the beginning of the survey. Add to that, the long-term benefits were also cited after their participation, and they were ensured that there were no associated risks after they answered the survey. Full informed consent was sought from the respondents by providing them with options to voluntarily participate or not, hence, no participating entity was coerced to be involved in the study. Moreover, any student who had responded may withdraw their answer from the study for any reason without citing any consequence as long as the data were not statistically treated yet. Lastly, it was ensured that all contents of the survey questionnaire and the manner of administration were not discriminatory nor offensive to any student in terms of their age, sex, or race, among others.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Student-Respondents

Table 1 presents the frequency distribution and percentage of the respondents (N=335) in terms of their age.

It is notable that the age bracket between 18 to 22 years old yielded the highest frequency of 307 (91.64%) which indicates most of the student respondents. This is due to the fact that the typical age range for college students in the Philippines starts at the age of 18 years old. Meanwhile, the lowest frequency is in the age bracket of 33 to 37 (n= 3; 0.90%). This is indicative that a certain minority of adult learners are being admitted to the College of Education to take their preferred undergraduate teacher education program.

Table 1.

Demographic Profile of the Student-Respondents (Age)

Age	Demographic Profile (N = 335)	Frequency and Percentage	
		n	%
18 – 22		307	91.64
23 – 27		17	5.07
28 – 32		8	2.39
33 – 37		3	0.90

Shown in Table 2 is the frequency distribution and percentage of the respondents in terms of their sex. It is evident that females yielded the highest frequency of 208 (62.09%). Meanwhile, the frequency for males is 127 (37.91%). This reveals that teacher education programs are mostly preferred by females.

Table 2.

Demographic Profile of the Student-Respondents (Sex)

Demographic Profile (N = 335)	Frequency and Percentage	
	<i>n</i>	%
Sex		
Male	127	37.91
Female	208	62.09

The frequency distribution and percentage of the respondents in terms of their year level are shown in Table 3. Among the four-year levels, 2nd year ($n = 114$; 34.03%) notably marked the highest frequency. On the other hand, 4th year yielded the lowest frequency ($n = 17$; 5.07%) because, among all of the year levels, this year level is the only one which is still under the previous curriculum due to the issuances of the revised teacher education curricula by the Commission on Higher Education and the K to 12 transitions in the Philippines.

Table 3.

Demographic Profile of the Student-Respondents (Year Level)

Demographic Profile (N = 335)	Frequency and Percentage	
	<i>n</i>	%
Year Level		
1st year	112	33.43
2nd year	114	34.03
3rd year	92	27.46
4th year	17	5.07

Shown in Table 4 is the frequency distribution and percentage of the respondents in terms of their degree program. The Bachelor of Secondary Education (English) has the highest frequency ($n = 77$; 22.99%) of all the degree programs while the Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education (Industrial Arts) has the lowest count ($n = 1$; 0.30%).

Table 4.

Demographic Profile of the Student-Respondents (Degree Program)

Demographic Profile (<i>N</i> = 335)	Frequency and Percentage	
	<i>n</i>	%
Degree Program		
Bachelor of Elementary Education	69	20.60
Bachelor of Physical Education	57	17.01
Bachelor of Secondary Education (English)	77	22.99
Bachelor of Secondary Education (Filipino)	64	19.10
Bachelor of Secondary Education (Mathematics)	14	4.18
Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education (Food and Service Management)	21	6.27
Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education (Garments, Fashion, and Technology)	2	0.60
Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education (Home Economics)	30	8.96
Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education (Industrial Arts)	1	0.30

Self-regulated Learning (SRL)

Student-respondents' SRL was assessed along five subscales namely: intrinsic goal orientation, confidence in learning, task value, control of learning beliefs, and effort regulation.

Table 5.

Intrinsic Goal Orientation

Benchmark Statements for Self-regulated Learning (SRL)	\bar{x}	SD	Verbal Description
Intrinsic Goal Orientation			
1. In a class, I prefer course materials that challenge me so I can learn new things.	6.09	0.86	Agree
2. In a class, I prefer course material that arouses my curiosity, even if it is difficult to learn.	5.98	0.90	Agree
3. The most satisfying thing for me in a course is trying to understand the content as thoroughly as possible.	6.33	0.83	Strongly Agree
4. When I have the opportunity, I choose course assignments that I can learn from even if I'm not sure I will get a good grade.	5.76	0.89	Agree
Weighted Mean	6.04	0.87	Agree

Shown in Table 5 are the mean, standard deviation, and verbal description of each item under the subscale, intrinsic goal orientation. With a weighted mean of 6.04 and a standard deviation of 0.87, the results denote that most of the student respondents ‘agreed’ with most of the items under this subscale. Zumbrunn et al. (2011) expounded the term ‘goal’ in a classroom setting as a) a short-term attainable goal where a student targets a high score in an exam and b) a long-term attainable goal where a student seeks a deeper understanding of the lesson. The items under the first subscale reflected in the questionnaire fall under long-term attainable goals of the student-respondents for they target a deeper understanding of a course and a course material despite the associated challenges. A high level of intrinsic goal orientation is said to be attained if a student plans personal significant goals and engages in challenging yet purposive formation of learning (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011b). Also, intrinsic goal orientation is an important factor in self-regulation (Cho et al., 2017; Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011a). Moreover, goal setting is a fundamental step of an academically effective form of learning called self-regulation (Layco, 2019). Of all the items, the statement “The most satisfying thing for me in a course is trying to understand the content as thoroughly as possible” got the highest mean which indicated that the student-respondents perceived a high sense of motivation in setting up their ultimate goal - an in-depth understanding of the course content.

As seen in Table 6, student-respondents generally ‘agreed’ with most of the items under the subscale ‘confidence in learning’ based on the weighted mean of 5.50 and a standard deviation of 1.12. A student who practices self-regulation elicits confidence (Cho et al., 2020; Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011b; Zamnah & Ruswana, 2019). Cho and Jonassen (2009) stated that self-regulated learners possess confidence in the use of self-mechanized learning strategies in order to overcome uncertainties. The four items measured student-respondents’ confidence in an online course and it turned out that they generally ‘agreed’ with most of them. Meanwhile, item number 2, “I’m certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in this online course” yielded the lowest mean yet still denotes that the respondents are confident in understanding the course materials even the most difficult ones. Therefore, results showed that student-respondents elicit confidence in learning which indicates that they practice self-regulation. Considering the claim of Layco (2017) that SRL plays a vital role in the academic performance

Table 6.

Confidence in Learning

Benchmark Statements for Self-regulated Learning (SRL)	\bar{x}	SD	Verbal Description
Confidence in Learning			
1. I believe I will receive an excellent grade in this online course.	5.58	1.08	Agree
2. I’m certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in this online course.	5.14	1.12	More or Less Agree
3. I’m confident I can do an excellent job on the assignments and activities in this online course.	5.53	1.12	Agree
4. I’m certain I can master the skills being taught in this online course.	5.76	1.16	Agree
Weighted Mean	5.50	1.12	Agree

of students, along with the inferences of Al-Hebaish (2012) that a high sense of self-confidence manifests a high sense of academic achievement, student-respondents are more likely to excel academically in their respective online courses and will have a meaningful academic journey, in the long run.

Table 7.

Task Value

Benchmark Statements for Self-regulated Learning (SRL)	\bar{x}	SD	Verbal Description
Task Value			
1. I think I will be able to use what I learn in this course for classroom teaching.	6.18	0.86	Strongly Agree
2. It is important for me to learn the course material in this online class.	6.37	0.85	Strongly Agree
3. I think the course material in this class is useful for me to learn.	6.12	0.93	Agree
4. Understanding the topics in this course is very important to me.	6.59	0.72	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	6.32	0.84	Strongly Agree

As displayed in Table 7, the student-respondents, in general, ‘strongly agreed’ with most of the items under the subscale, ‘task value’ with a weighted mean of 6.32 and standard deviation of 0.84. If one is to grasp the very essence of self-regulation in learning, the quality of task value is a must (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011b; Cho et al., 2017). Students who possess a high sense of value in doing tasks are more likely to engage themselves in meaningful goal setting and systematized evaluation of learning through the strategic effort of goal accomplishment (Lawanto et al., 2014). Results further indicate that the student-respondents consider ‘task value’ as they meticulously prepare themselves to understand the course content.

Table 8.

Control of Learning Beliefs

Benchmark Statements for Self-regulated Learning (SRL)	\bar{x}	SD	Verbal Description
Control of Learning Beliefs			
1. If I study in appropriate ways, then I will be able to learn the topics covered in this course.	6.42	0.69	Strongly Agree
2. It will be my own fault if I don't learn the course topics.	5.81	1.21	Agree
3. If I try hard enough, I will learn more about educational technologies.	6.41	0.77	Strongly Agree
4. If I don't learn the educational technologies taught in this online course, it probably is because I didn't try hard enough.	5.75	1.21	Agree
Weighted Mean	6.10	0.97	Agree

As revealed in Table 8, the subscale ‘control of learning beliefs’ yielded a weighted mean of 6.10 and a standard deviation of 0.97. This signifies that student-respondents generally ‘agreed’ with most of the items. Hence, in order to become a sophisticated learner (effective as a learner), one must know how to monitor their state of learning and control learning activities corresponding to the monitoring act (Bjork et al., 2013). In self-regulation, control of learning beliefs is entwined with confidence. Cho et al. (2017) described ‘control of learning beliefs’ as the act by which students believe that they are in control of their learning and therefore have a higher chance to initiate attainable learning goals, monitor learning progress, and adjust their learning process based on the outcome of the process. Moreover, control of learning beliefs is the perception

of a self-regulated learner of obtaining positive and meaningful results towards the end of an endeavor (Sen & Yilmaz, 2016). With a weighted mean of 6.10, the student-respondents, therefore, know how to control their learning beliefs. Subsequently, among all the items, the statement “If I try hard enough, I will learn more about educational technologies” marked the highest mean of 6.41 which indicates that the respondents are eager to learn more in their respective online courses if they strive harder.

Table 9.

Effort Regulation

Benchmark Statements for Self-regulated Learning (SRL)	\bar{x}	SD	Verbal Description
Effort Regulation			
1. I often feel so lazy or bored when I study that I quit before I finish what I planned to do. (Reverse Coding)	4.74	1.67	More or Less Disagree
2. I work hard to do well even if I don't like what we are doing.	5.76	1.07	Agree
3. When the coursework is difficult, I either give up or only study the easy parts.	4.25	1.79	Undecided
4. Even when course materials are dull and uninteresting, I manage to keep working until I finish.	6.00	1.07	Agree
Weighted Mean	5.19	1.56	More or Less Agree

With a mean of 5.19 and a standard deviation of 1.56, student-respondents ‘more or less agreed’ with most of the items under the subscale, ‘effort regulation’ as evidenced in Table 3. Effort regulation is defined as the extent by which a learner keeps on striving and exerting effort despite academic challenges (Broadbent & Poon, 2015). In an online classroom, numerous challenges have been emerging as these impact the students’ intrinsic motivation to learn. However, Cho et al. (2017) confirmed that despite the lack of intrinsic motivation, students who practice self-regulation can manage effort and accomplish tasks strategically. Moreover, effort regulation (resource management strategies) is the act of obtaining the objectives with determination to maintain attention despite uninteresting tasks or other associated difficulties (Sen & Yilmaz, 2016). With the results obtained from the questionnaire, the student-respondents somehow know how to strategically manage their effort to learn. Pointing out the item statement “I often feel so lazy or bored when I study that I quit before I finish what I planned to do”, considering a reverse coding to analyze the student respondents' answer in this particular statement, shows that they are eager to finish what they have planned to do. However as appeared in the item “When the course work is difficult, I either give up or only study the easy parts” where reverse coding was also used, the respondents revealed that they are not quite sure what to do if pinned in such a situation.

Self-regulated learning has been a pressing issue of concern being discussed across the disciplines of educational research since it was proven to be associated with other factors such as academic achievement (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011a; Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011b; Zumbunn et al., 2011; Broadbent & Poon, 2015; Alghamdia et al., 2019; Alotaibi et al., 2017), mathematical performance (Cleary & Kitsantas, 2017; Layco, 2020), English language proficiency (Bai & Wang, 2020), community of inquiry (Cho et al., 2017), and the list goes on indicating that SRL of students are in need to be assessed. In relation to this, the empirical results of this study revealed that student-respondents are practicing self-regulation since they generally ‘agreed’ with most of the items under the

five (5) subscales.

Community of Inquiry (CoI)

Student-respondents' Community of Inquiry (CoI) was described along the following subscales such as social presence, cognitive presence, and teaching presence.

Table 10.

Social Presence

Benchmark Statements for Community of Inquiry (CoI)	\bar{x}	SD	Verbal Description
Social Presence			
1. In general, I felt connected with others in the course.	5.62	1.14	Agree
2. I felt I was encouraged to engage in the learning activities.	5.81	0.97	Agree
3. Online communication is an excellent medium for social interaction.	5.33	1.34	Agree
4. I felt comfortable conversing through the online medium.	5.15	1.28	More or Less Agree
5. I felt comfortable participating in the course discussions.	5.33	1.24	Agree
6. I felt comfortable posting questions.	5.01	1.33	More or Less Agree
7. I felt comfortable disagreeing with other course participants.	4.36	1.51	Undecided
Weighted Mean	5.23	1.26	More or Less Agree

As gleaned in Table 10, the student-respondents 'more or less agreed' with most of the items under the subscale, 'social presence' with a mean of 5.23 and a standard deviation of 1.26. Dhawan (2020) pointed out that the 'human touch' is lacking in a virtual learning environment, and this is considered vital, be it face-to-face or online. Social presence is responsible for projecting one's personal identity in a learning environment. Moreover, it is the ability of a person to associate positive interaction through cyberspace (Garrison & Akyol, 2011; Kreijin et al., 2014). The online learning environment tends to limit social interaction. However, Kreijin et al. (2014) stated that the level of the realness of a person in online communication affects social presence. In addition, Kreijin et al. (2014) further posited that when using an equal medium of communication, the social presence may not be immediately apparent and needs time to develop. On the other hand, as argued by Garrison & Akyol (2011), the role of the social presence in the CoI Framework (Cho et al., 2017) is not just to foster a sense of belongingness, but rather to support critical inquiry resulting in meaningful learning. Results further indicate that the student-respondents consider social presence which indicates that they support each other in an online community. The statement "I felt I was encouraged to engage in the learning activities" clearly shows that the respondents are encouraged to participate and engage in learning activities. Meanwhile, the item "I felt comfortable disagreeing with other course participants" reveals that the respondents are not certain as to what is needed to be done in this situation. Some may easily express that they disagree with other course participants with ease, but others do not. In general, the student-respondents are engaged to attain learning.

Table 11.

Cognitive Presence

Benchmark Statements for Community of Inquiry (CoI)	\bar{x}	SD	Verbal Description
Cognitive Presence			
1. The topics stimulated my interest in the course.	5.84	0.85	Agree
2. Course activities stimulated my curiosity about the weekly topic.	5.78	0.84	Agree
3. I was given ample opportunities to learn.	5.87	0.96	Agree
4. I have learned a lot in this course.	6.09	0.87	Agree
5. I felt motivated to explore course-related topics.	6.01	0.94	Agree
6. I can apply the skills developed in this course to my work.	6.20	0.86	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	5.97	0.89	Agree

As seen in Table 11, student-respondents generally ‘agreed’ with most of the items under the subscale, ‘cognitive presence’ with a weighted mean of 5.97 and standard deviation of 0.89. Cognitive presence is a major part of the CoI framework (Cho et al., 2017). This subscale allows the students to construct meaningful thoughts through engagement in a collaborative discussion (Garrison & Akyol, 2011; Cho et al., 2017). These thoughts are vital in achieving a meaningful educational experience. In fact, Cho et al. (2017) emphasized the importance of cognitive presence in the CoI framework for it allows the course participants to acquire thoughts. Afterwards, these thoughts acquired in a collaborative discussion are developed and reflected by the participants resulting in knowledge acquisition and meaningful educational experiences (Garrison & Akyol, 2011). Based on the results, the respondents tend to acquire thoughts and develop these thoughts into learning acquired from a meaningful discourse. The item “I can apply skills developed in this course to my work” marked the highest mean ($\bar{x} = 6.20$) in this subscale revealing that the respondents are optimistic about acquiring skills needed for future ventures as professionals.

Indicated in Table 12 is a weighted mean of 6.27 and a standard deviation of 0.79 indicating that the student-respondents ‘strongly agreed’ with all the items under the subscale, ‘teaching presence’. In order to achieve a worthwhile educational experience, teaching presence plays the key role in the cultivation of social and cognitive presences (Cho et al., 2017). Garrison & Akyol (2011) defined teaching presence as designing, facilitating, and directing cognitive and social presences to realize personal significant learning outcomes. The results reveal that student-respondents consider teaching presence as vital. The item “The instructor cared about my learning” garnered the highest mean ($\bar{x} = 6.37$) which shows that the respondents are feeling the presence of the teacher in their online courses. They are getting the support they need to have fruitful learning experiences.

Table 12.

Teaching Presence

Benchmark Statements for Community of Inquiry (Col)	\bar{x}	SD	Verbal Description
Teaching Presence			
1. The instructor clearly communicated important course topics.	6.20	0.79	Strongly Agree
2. The instructor clearly communicated important course goals.	6.25	0.74	Strongly Agree
3. The instructor provided clear instructions on how to participate in course learning activities.	6.23	0.82	Strongly Agree
4. The instructor communicated important due dates and time frames for learning activities and assignments.	6.31	0.79	Strongly Agree
5. My instructor presented helpful examples that allowed me to better understand the content of the course.	6.31	0.80	Strongly Agree
6. My instructor clearly explained the content of the course.	6.31	0.76	Strongly Agree
7. The instructor helped keep me on task.	6.20	0.81	Strongly Agree
8. The instructor encouraged me to develop new skills in this course.	6.27	0.82	Strongly Agree
9. The instructor was responsive to my questions	6.21	0.83	Strongly Agree
10. The instructor cared about my learning.	6.37	0.73	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	6.27	0.79	Strongly Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	5.82	0.98	Agree

Online Learning Readiness (OLR)

Student-respondents' OLR was described based on the following subscales, namely: computer/internet self-efficacy, self-directed learning, learner control, motivation for learning, and online communication self-efficacy.

Table 13.

Computer/Internet Self-efficacy

Benchmark Statements for Online Learning Readiness (OLR)	\bar{x}	SD	VD
Student-Respondents' Computer/Internet Self-efficacy			
1. I feel confident in performing the basic functions of Microsoft Office programs	4.79	0.96	Agree
2. I feel confident in my knowledge and skills in how to manage online learning.	4.81	0.93	Agree
3. I feel confident in using the Internet to find information	4.99	0.89	Agree

Grand Weighted Mean	4.86	0.93	Agree
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Table 13 revealed that the student-respondents mostly 'agreed' with the items under the subscale, 'computer/internet self-efficacy' with a weighted mean of 4.86 and a standard deviation of 0.93. Relating to technical skills, which involves confidence in using computer-related resources and the internet for a successful skill demonstration (Hung et al., 2010; Cigdem, 2014), computer/internet self-efficacy is one of the five subscales to be considered in assessing students' online learning readiness. Table 5 indicates that the student-respondents possess a sense of confidence in terms of executing basic Microsoft Office programs (see item no. 1) which is necessary in an online course. Also, they are confident that their prior knowledge is of big help in their respective online courses (see item no. 2). Moreover, they elicit confidence in using the internet as a resource of information (see item no. 3).

Table 14.

Self-directed Learning

Benchmark Statements for Online Learning Readiness (OLR)	\bar{x}	SD	VD
Student-Respondents' Self-directed Learning			
1. I can carry out my study plan while learning online.	4.91	0.84	Agree
2. I seek assistance when facing learning problems from lecturers and friends.	5.10	0.89	Agree
3. I manage my time well while learning online.	4.88	0.99	Agree
4. I set up my personal online learning goals for each lesson.	4.99	0.92	Agree
5. I have a high expectation for my learning performance.	4.77	0.95	Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	4.93	0.92	Agree

Shown in Table 14 are the mean ($\bar{x} = 4.93$), standard deviation ($SD = 0.92$), and verbal description of each item under the subscale 'self-directed learning'. Empirical results show that the student-respondents generally 'agreed' with all of the items under self-directed learning. Self-directed learning is defined as the control of oneself towards learning opportunities. Self-directed learners go after narrowly defined personal learning needs and interact with others to achieve learning goals (Hammond & Collins, 2013; Chung et al., 2020). With respect to Table 5, the student-respondents are engaged in making study plans that are personal to address their needs in their online courses (see item no. 1). Among all of the items, the statement "I seek assistance when facing learning problems from lecturers and friends" marked the highest mean (5.10) which means that the student-respondents are interacting with their friends and lecturers to solve learning problems and achieve their learning goals.

Table 15.

Learner Control

Benchmark Statements for Online Learning Readiness (OLR)	\bar{x}	SD	VD
Student-Respondents' Learner Control			
1. I can manage my learning progress while learning online	4.96	0.80	Agree
2. I am not distracted by other online social activities (Insta, FB etc) while learning	4.01	1.41	Slightly Agree

3. I repeated/replay the online learning materials based on my needs	4.95	0.98	Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	4.64	1.06	Agree

Table 15 shows the weighted mean (\bar{x} = 4.64) and standard deviation (SD = 1.06) under the subscale, 'learner control'. These reveal that student respondents generally 'agreed' with most of the items under the said subscale. Learner control, in fact, is the ability of the student to resist and manage online-related distractions (Chung et al., 2020). The item "I am not distracted by other online social activities (Insta, FB, etc) while learning" marked the lowest mean (4.01) signifying that student-respondents are somehow not distracted by social networking sites while they are learning. On the other hand, the item "I can manage my learning progress while learning online" marked the highest mean which means that student-respondents can manage and control their progress in learning. Subsequently, a lack of learner control is one of the reasons why students are not yet ready to learn on an online platform (Chung et al., 2020).

Table 16.
Motivation for Learning

Benchmark Statements for Online Learning Readiness (OLR)	\bar{x}	SD	VD
Student-Respondents' Motivation for Learning			
1. I am open to new ideas when learning online.	5.44	0.68	Strongly Agree
2. I am motivated to do online learning.	4.88	0.93	Agree
3. While learning online, I learn to improve from my previous mistakes.	5.17	0.83	Strongly Agree
4. I like to share my ideas with my friends while learning online.	5.20	0.81	Strongly Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	5.17	0.81	Strongly Agree

As gleaned in Table 16, many of the student-respondents 'strongly agreed' with most of the items under the subscale 'motivation for learning' as justified by the weighted mean of 5.17 and a standard deviation of 0.81. Considering the point of view of the students, motivation for learning can be referred to as the acquisition of a higher score in exams, getting rewards, as well as having a deep understanding of the learning content (Cigdem, 2014; Chung et al., 2020). Referring to Table 16, student-respondents are eager to bounce back from their failures which is a sign of motivation to learn despite the challenges in an online environment (i.e. item 1). Meanwhile, the item "I am open to new ideas when learning online" obtained the highest mean (5.44) showing that student-respondents are motivated to new opportunities to learn in an online environment.

Table 17.
Online Communication Self-efficacy

Benchmark Statements for Online Learning Readiness (OLR)	\bar{x}	SD	VD
Student-Respondents' Online Communication Self-efficacy			
1. I feel confident in using online tools to communicate with my lecturer.	4.77	0.99	Agree
2. I feel confident in expressing my thoughts through online text messages/ posting comments in WhatsApp/ Google Classroom.	4.66	1.09	Agree
3. I feel confident in posting questions in online discussions.	4.50	1.07	Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	4.64	1.05	Agree

As shown in Table 17, the general weighted mean ($\bar{x} = 4.59$) and standard deviation ($SD = 1.08$) denoted that the student-respondents generally ‘agreed’ with most of the items under the subscale, ‘online communication self-efficacy’. If one is to grasp the very essence of OLR, online communication self-efficacy is one of the subscales to be considered. It promotes students’ confidence in expressing thoughts in an online environment (Chung et al., 2020) and computer-mediated communication (Cigdem, 2014). As indicated in Table 5, student-respondents are confident in expressing their thoughts through online platforms (i.e. item 2) as well as confident in posting questions during online discussions (i.e. item 3). Meanwhile, under behavioral intention, student-respondents somehow want to pursue online learning in the next semester if they are given a choice (see item no. 5). Of all the items, the item “I feel confident in using online tools to communicate with my lecturer” marked the highest mean (4.77) which means that student-respondents are confident in using computer-mediated communication.

Differences Between the Respondents’ SRL, CoI, and OLR when grouped according to their Profile

Differences in terms of sex

T-test was used to examine differences between and among student respondents SRL, CoI, and OLR when grouped according to sex. Table 6 revealed the t-test values and the equivalent p-values on the test of differences in the assessment of the three groups as they were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The p-values for SRL ($0.72 > 0.05$), CoI ($0.74 > 0.05$), and OLR ($0.40 > 0.05$) indicate that there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that the assessment of the student respondents’ levels of SRL, CoI, and OLR do not signify substantial differences when grouped according to sex. This result contradicts the study of Alghamdi et al. (2019) who revealed significant differences among Arabian respondents’ SRL level when grouped according to sex where females are more engaged in self-regulated behaviors than males. Also, studies conducted by Firat and Bozkurt (2020) reported that Turkish female students elicit higher levels of OLR than their male counterparts. These also corroborate with the study of Chung et al. (2020) that Malaysian female students have higher levels of OLR than their male counterparts. Moreover, Khodabandelou et al. (2014) found that there is a significant difference between Malaysian male and female students’ CoI assessment.

Table 18.

Results of T-Test of Significant Variations among Student-respondents’ Self-regulated Learning, Community of Inquiry and Online Learning Readiness when grouped according to sex

Variables	Self-regulated Learning			Community of Inquiry			Online Learning Readiness		
	t	p	Decision	t	p	Decision	t	p	Decision
Sex	0.13	0.72	Do not Reject H ₀	0.11	0.74	Do not Reject H ₀	0.40	0.40	Do not Reject H ₀

The difference is significant at 0.05

Differences in terms of age

One of the objectives of this study is to figure out if there is significant variation among student respondents SRL, CoI, and OLR when grouped according to their age. Table 19 unveiled the p-values on the test of variation on the assessment of the

three groups, tested at 0.05 level of significance via analysis of variance (ANOVA). The p-values of SRL (0.98 > 0.05), CoI (0.40 > 0.05), and OLR (0.08 > 0.05) indicate insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This means that the assessment of the student respondents SRL, CoI, and OLR do not signify substantial differences when grouped according to age. This contrasts with Firat and Bozkurt (2020) in OLR, wherein their findings revealed that Turkish adult learners are more ready for online learning than youngsters. Meanwhile, Price et al. (2011) claimed such difference between American young adults and older adults' SRL. Also, Wicks et al. (2015) pointed out that there is a significant difference in American students' level of CoI when grouped according to their age.

Differences in terms of year levels

Table 19 also unveiled the p-values on the test of variation on the assessment of the three groups, tested at 0.05 level of significance. As shown in Table 19, the p-values for SRL (0.22 > 0.05) and OLR (0.23 > 0.05) indicate insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This means that the assessment of the student respondents' levels of SRL and OLR do not signify substantial differences when grouped according to year level. However, gleaned from Table 7, the p-value for CoI (0.00 < 0.05) implies the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, the assessment of the student respondents' levels of CoI signifies a significant difference when grouped according to their year levels.

Differences in terms of degree programs

Table 19 shows the p-values on the test of variation on the assessment of the three groups, tested at 0.05 level of significance. The p-values for SRL (0.59 > 0.05), CoI (0.15 > 0.05), and OLR (0.63 > 0.05) indicate insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that the assessment of the student respondents' levels of SRL, CoI, and OLR does not signify substantial differences when grouped according to degree program.

Table 19.

Results of ANOVA Test of Significant Variations among Student-respondents' Self-regulated Learning, Community of Inquiry and Online Learning Readiness when grouped according to Age, Year Level, and Degree Program

Variable	Self-regulated Learning			Community of Inquiry			Online Learning Readiness		
	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>	Decision	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>	Decision	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>	Decision
Age	0.38	0.98	Do not Reject H_0	1.80	0.40	Do not Reject H_0	1.62	0.08	Do Not Reject H_0
Year Level	1.49	0.22	Do not Reject H_0	8.69	0.00	Reject H_0	3.22	0.23	Do not Reject H_0
Degree Program	0.82	0.59	Do not Reject H_0	1.52	0.15	Do not Reject H_0	0.76	0.63	Do not Reject H_0

The difference is significant at 0.05.

Relationship Between SRL and CoI

The Pearson's r Test of the Relationship between the student respondents' self-regulated learning and community of inquiry yielded a p -value of 0.00 which is less than the level of significance set at 0.01, hence, indicates that it is sufficient to say that there is a significant relationship between self-regulated learning and community of inquiry. This means that the higher the assessment of the student respondents' SRL, the higher their assessment of their perceived CoI, as well. Subsequently, the higher the student-respondents' SRL level, the higher their assessment of their CoI. With that, since student respondents marked a high sense of "intrinsic goal orientation, confidence in learning, task value, control of learning beliefs, and effort regulation", they also marked high levels of "social presence, cognitive presence, and teaching presence" in an online platform. Presumably, participation in a meaningful discourse allows them to gain fruitful learning which contributes to their self-regulation. Likewise, student-respondents' systematic and self-regulated thoughts allow them to engage and contribute to a collaborative discourse leading to a meaningful educational experience. This is somewhat consistent with the inference of Cho et al. (2017) that in an online course, students who understand and develop their self-regulatory efforts could fruitfully contribute to the formation and development of positive learning. Shea and Bidjerano (2012) asserted the SRL-CoI relationship where they concluded that students who self-regulate their learning know how to actively participate in a meaningful discourse (CoI).

Relationship between SRL and OLR

The Pearson's r Test for the Relationship between student-respondents' self-regulated learning and online learning readiness yielded a p -value of 0.00 which is less than the level of significance set at 0.01. Therefore, it is sufficient to say that there is a moderate positive relationship between self-regulated learning and online learning readiness. Adam et al. (2017) emphasized the importance of learner control in relation to self-regulation in an online course. Learner control gives an opportunity to stay focused on learning goals (intrinsic goal orientation), develops confidence to attain learning goals (confidence in learning), realizes significant tasks (task value), delimits computer-related distractions by monitoring learning progress (control of learning beliefs) and encourages perseverance to achieve the realized goals (effort regulation). In addition to learner control, computer/internet self-efficacy plays a vital role in self-regulation (Wang et al., 2013). If one is to grasp the very essence of SRL strategies in online learning, students must possess confidence in skill demonstration. Moreover, excellent communication can promote self-efficacy in an online environment which is necessary to master SRL strategies (Lock et al., 2017). A high level of online communication self-efficacy provides feedback which is necessary in self-regulation. Also, Sansone et al. (2011) pointed out the importance of motivation in online learning which contributes to the readiness of the students. In addition to these, SRL plays a major role in developing self-directed learning (Bell, 2017). High levels of SRL increase more autonomous/self-directed learning.

As Philippine news reports underscored the lack of readiness of Filipino students in online learning (Kritz, 2020), students must realize the importance of SRL to cope with online-related uncertainties and achieve the goal of having meaningful and fruitful educational experiences in online learning (Layco, 2017). The results of this study may be considered as a steppingstone for further research in exploring the relationship between SRL and OLR especially in the timely context of the paradigm shift in the Philippine education system.

Table 20.

Test of Correlation among student-respondents self-regulated learning to community of inquiry and self-regulated learning to online learning readiness

Variables	Self-regulated Learning				
	Pearson r -value	Degree of Relationship	p -value	Decision	Interpretation
Community of Inquiry	0.63**	Moderate Positive Correlation	0.00	Reject the H_0	Significant
Online Learning Readiness	0.56**	Moderate Positive Correlation	0.00	Reject the H_0	Significant

Correlation is significant at 0.01.

Table 21.

Proposed Inputs toward an Enhanced Online Learning Delivery

Self-Regulated Learning	
Community of Inquiry	Online Learning Readiness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Communicate with the students especially when they seek teaching presence and necessary support. ▪ Optimize course activities that will stimulate students' interest leading to the development of new skills in cyberspace. ▪ Measure students' ability to engage in a meaningful discourse leading to fruitful learning experiences through the administration of community of inquiry assessment tool. ▪ Motivate the students to post questions be it in a synchronous or asynchronous session. ▪ Use andragogy-based synchronous and asynchronous approaches to build a harmonious relationship in a community of learning. ▪ Necessitate cooperation and unity through establishing rapport. ▪ Incorporate collaborative learning strategies. ▪ Target students' engagement in a collaborative discourse by encouraging them to join in various college/university forums, seminars, colloquiums, among others. ▪ Yield a productive, meaningful, and fruitful learning experience in cyberspace through online discussion forums (ODFs) on critical topics to allow students to establish self-identity and presence in a community of learners. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organize high interaction course activities. ▪ Narrowly define students' personal learning needs by interacting with them through computer-mediated communication. ▪ Let students take charge of their learning through the incorporation of metacognitive strategies. ▪ Improve students' self-efficacy by allowing them to post questions be it in a synchronous or asynchronous class. ▪ Navigate and plan instruction targeting students' online communication self-efficacy. ▪ Encourage students to be proactive, taking into the responsibility of their own learning experiences. ▪ Remind the students with their limitations in internet usage especially online social networking sites. ▪ Encourage students to resist and manage online related distractions. ▪ Assess students' online learning readiness through the administration of the online readiness assessment tool. ▪ Develop students' confidence in executing computer-related skills through online course requirements. ▪ Yield a well-equipped, well-prepared, and well-defined online environment enhancing students' readiness in online learning.

One of the purposes of this study was to collect empirical evidence which can be used as inputs for the college being considered as the locale of the study to continuously update its online learning delivery and learning continuity plan. Table

21 summarizes the proposed inputs for an enhanced online learning delivery. Since the results of this study revealed significant differences in terms of the assessment of their CoI among different year levels, instructors/professors may focus on developing a community of inquiry as a starting point in every online course through the following suggested inputs. Moreover, since a significant moderate positive relationship was seen among the variables, this interconnection justified the essence and the need to consider these psychological constructs in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of the curriculum in the online learning context.

Conclusions

The majority of the student-respondents fall within the age bracket of 18–22 years old, with the least being in the 33–37 age range. Most respondents are females, predominantly second-year students, while fourth-year students constitute the least. Additionally, the BSEd English program had the highest number of respondents, whereas the BTVTEd Industrial Arts program had the least. In terms of self-regulated learning (SRL), the respondents generally ‘agreed’ with most items under the five subscales, particularly intrinsic goal orientation, confidence in learning, and control of learning beliefs. They ‘strongly agreed’ with items under the task value subscale but only ‘more or less agreed’ with items related to effort regulation. Similarly, under the Community of Inquiry (CoI), most respondents ‘agreed’ with the subscales, with a majority ‘strongly agreeing’ with teaching presence, while cognitive presence garnered agreement, and social presence received ‘more or less agreement.’ Regarding online learning readiness (OLR), the respondents generally ‘agreed’ with subscales such as computer/internet self-efficacy, self-directed learning, learner control, and online communication self-efficacy, while ‘strongly agreeing’ with motivation for learning. Statistically, there were no significant differences in SRL, CoI, and OLR when grouped by age, sex, or degree program. However, CoI showed a significant difference when grouped by year level, while SRL and OLR did not. Lastly, a positive moderate relationship was identified between SRL and CoI, as well as between SRL and OLR.

Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions of this study, several recommendations are proposed. Since the research focused solely on teacher education students, it is suggested that future studies include college students from other programs to explore their self-regulated learning (SRL), community of inquiry (CoI), and online learning readiness (OLR). Additionally, while this study examined the interconnections between SRL and CoI, and SRL and OLR, future research could further investigate the relationship between CoI and OLR. Educators should also undergo training in online learning pedagogies and the integration of Interactive and Adaptive Learning Technologies to personalize students’ learning experiences according to their readiness and progress. Faculty members in teacher education institutions should explore diverse strategies to enhance their students’ SRL through improved online learning environments. Lastly, future research is encouraged to include other demographic variables beyond age, sex, year level, and degree program to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the interconnections between SRL, CoI, and OLR.

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